

Phuket mascot design from based on cultural value

Jirawat Sookkaew¹, Nakarin Chaikaew², Pipatpong Saephoo³

¹Department of Computer Graphic and Multimedia, School of Information and Communication Technology, University of Phayao, Phayao, Thailand

²Research Unit of Spatial Innovation Development, School of Information and Communication Technology, University of Phayao, Phayao, Thailand

³Department of Digital Business, School of Information and Communication Technology, University of Phayao, Phayao, Thailand

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ABSTRACT

Designing with cultural, wisdom, way of life, beliefs, and other values that have been passed down through generations. Let's produce a creative product that is entertaining and varied. One of them is to design a mascot to be used in the media as a character and representation of something, and to imply that this mascot will be able to act on behalf of those representatives. It is clear that Phuket has an exceptional and valuable cultural capital. In addition, there are numerous traditions, rituals, beliefs, customs, arts, and civilizations that are indigenous to the local population. It was thought that this study did a good job of figuring out how to use cultural values to make characters by applying design theory or design science to creativity. It also did a good job of figuring out how applicable the methods and design approaches were.

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Corresponding Author:

Jirawat Sookkaew

Department of Computer graphic and multimedia, School of Information and Communication Technology

University of Phayao

Phayao, Thailand

Email: Jirawat.so@up.ac.th

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea of providing value in cultural dimensions, wisdom, way of life, beliefs, and other values passed down through generations for use in design and inspiration for many creative professions. It now serves a wider and more vital purpose. These principles are essential for boosting the economy and advancing the community's arts and culture on a national and international level as a selling point and knowledge base expander for a wider range of people. Incorporating the concept of cultural materials and intellectual information into the creative process, or building a new creative conceptual framework, enables these things to be inherited and transmitted more broadly and simply in accordance with the times. The creation of a mascot is another method for producing an instantly recognizable and auspicious picture. A "mascot" is a creature or thing, typically an animal, object, or human character, used to present or represent something to the public as a character and representative of something in order to express and convey that character that can act on behalf of those agents, agencies, attractions, merchandise, and products. Currently, the concept is being implemented more frequently in corporate communication by establishing a mascot to be utilized as a representative in presentations. This includes both creative and non-creative variables and methods for developing characters for a variety of designs. Mascots are useful for building a positive image in the eyes of the public by creating characters in 2D and 3D, incorporating movement and expressing emotions. Using cartoon characters, such as mascots, in marketing will help the product or business feel good to bigger groups of consumers who can easily access the business or product through the mascot. Make it simpler for customers to recall products.

Phuket is a province that is abundant in many ways, including well-known tourism resources that are recognized and cherished worldwide, especially for its spectacular beaches and seas, hotels and services, and vacation locations. There are also outstanding and useful cultural capitals, such as the Peranakans in Phuket, who recognize that both Chinese and Malay women and men refer to themselves as "ba ba," while "Yaya" has also expanded their culture. This growing culture is referred to as "Peranakan culture," and it is seen as a group that conveys a special type of holiness to the people of Phuket, in addition to being prominent in art and culture. Phuket was designated a "City of Gastronomy" by UNESCO in December 2015, placing it on par with 17 other places throughout the world that have gained the same international recognition [1]. Another defining aspect of architecture is the building style. In Thailand, "Sino-Portuguese" architecture is characterized by a combination of European and Chinese characteristics and is known as "colonial architecture" or "colonial buildings." There is Sino-Portuguese architecture in Ranong city, Krabi city, Takua Pa city, Phang Nga city, and Trang city. These structures, especially the stucco designs used to decorate them, tell the story of the terrain, climate, history, and ethnic society that coexist. A story about the history of oriental decorations is also presented [2]. Additionally, there are a variety of local customs, rituals, beliefs, traditions, arts, and cultures, proving that Phuket has a wide range of narratives and cultural styles. In the former, culture serves as a mediator between the other components of sustainability, balancing competing and conflicting demands and guiding ecological, economic, and social policies toward their objectives [3]. Appropriate for revealing the secrets of the universe's numerous tales. Our endeavors in digital cultural heritage could not have been established by a single individual, but rather by a multidisciplinary team comprised of experts in the humanities, anthropology, media arts, technology, design, and digital production methods [4].

Currently, people's lives are intertwined with technology and creation. Using creative tools in computer graphics and technology combined with the process of creating visual art results for transmission is another aspect of preserving and transmitting art and culture through the use of technology and the popularity of the people. Specifically, the usage of character creation tools. Designers can look at elements and use them to come up with new ideas or design characters for a wide range of media. Character design and building for portrayal requires the creation of work components into an attractive character. Consequently, the design of digital character production entails both design and model analysis procedures. Creating and adorning objects while incorporating these principles and procedures into the actions, methods, and tools of computer-based graphic design. For the mascot character process to work as planned, both the study of the knowledge to be taught and the technological process that will be used on the character must be done at the same time. This will help keep as much of the character's individuality as possible.

Access to digital media is far greater than access to traditional media, and this is reflected in the content and viewing preferences of contemporary people. Modern society is inevitably influenced by digital instruments. Therefore, it is brief; at this point, a second technique is essential. For delivering messages or expressing information in the present period, the use of symbols and accessibility in designing and generating media for viewers is essential. Therefore, creating agents or symbols is essential for communicating information and increasing attention. By allowing the ingredients and beauty of a valuable culture to exist and circulate through the multiple media channels of the connected world, we are able to adapt and apply these digital technologies in new, more people-centered ways on a broader scale. The objective of this paper was include. To investigate the importance of arts and culture, which is a distinguishing element of Phuket city and design a character based on Phuket Town's distinct artistic and cultural identity. Developing a brand character or mascot is an excellent way to establish a corporate identity and attract public attention. A mascot can provide virtually limitless opportunities to increase consumer interest and recognition. The mascot's creation and implementation are critical to its success [5].

As a result, the researcher has used the diverse cultural values that exist in Phuket to create a mascot character using creative forms from computer graphics to be able to use in creativity for further development and to convey Phuket in art and culture by assisting in the creation of a look, including bringing art and cultural capital from the next generation to the Phuket people's society and culture, and as a guide for future research projects.

2. THE PROPOSED METHOD

2.1. The guide for design

a) Designed using knowledge of animal and human anatomy. When deciding on a character's traits based on the idea of character creation, using character design based on the idea of character creation, it's important to keep in mind the following strategies for making life:

- Personification entails imbuing inanimate objects with human attributes. There are three fundamental types of personification. i) anthromorphism, ii) zoomorphism, and iii) teramorphism.
- In numerous ways, a mascot can symbolize a product or brand. The "literal" method, wherein a mascot adopts one or more fundamental brand characteristics, anthropomorphizes them, and depicts them as a character [6].

- The most important aspect when changing normal photographs to exaggerated designs such as large noses, wide lips, and tails is the figure's personality and originality, which allows recognition and interpretation of the intended message using computer graphics software [7].
- b) The principles and qualities of the mascots we encounter can be classified as follows.
 - Characteristics of a person's shape.
 - Pictures of vegetables, fruits, and plants.
 - Objects.
 - Pictures of animals.
- c) Shape Language is a concept: Using basic forms as a creative element to portray the meaning of the characters, such shapes can convey the characters' sentiments and touches [8].
 - Circles are organic and natural shapes. Round out edges and add curves to evoke a warm and welcoming feeling.
 - Square off things like jaws, shoulders, and even hands—they not only feel strong, but can feel difficult to move.
 - Triangles are sharp. Exaggerating the size and length of these shapes can heighten fear and transform how menacing the character is.

This often appears in the creation shape or design that we see until we are used to both graphic design and the nature of the proportions and elements of the shapes that we find in various designs. Work on product design or other designs from the shape example in Figure 1. Each shape can convey different meanings. This shape can be modified to be a similar shape for suitability in design.

Figure 1. Interpretation of shapes used in character design [8]

- d) Use simple shapes: Designer play with the proportions on different parts of the body to give your character a unique style. Try changing the proportions of you character in size, weight, and height
- e) Categories of character design:
 - Logo: Simplistic, Cute (big eyes, small noses)
 - Simple: More complex than logo but still very simple, Stronger forms
 - Ordinary: Rich variety of expressions, Suitable for media such as animation
 - Complicated: Proportions and expressions of character are closer to reality, Used by Disney
 - Realistic: The closest to realism, found in Hollywood blockbusters and high-definition games, intended to awe the audience and provide a sense of reality [9]
- f) Super-Deformed (Chibi) character body structure model. It is also used to manufacture character figures and mascots as shown in Figure 2. For comedic effect, characters in several video games and CG films are occasionally designed in the SD style. Therefore, designing a super-deformed counterpart (SD style) of a standard character model is a typical and essential task for visual artists and graphic designers. The SD style is a popular artistic technique in the animation industry. Various creative styles have been attained through the application of numerous specified methodologies [10]

Using proportions in the super-deformed form it is also the shape and proportion of the character creation that can be built on and easily shaped to meet the designer's proportions as well as the gentle proportions. Cute appears friendly and has a wide range of appeal. By the gestures and performances of the model proportions super-deformed the image below illustrates the character's appearance and demeanor very well.

Drawing super-deformed (Chibi) characters is extremely helpful for drawing regular characters as well.

 - Characters' facial expressions become more varied and dramatic.
 - It helps you study how the human body moves.
 - It is useful for not only dynamic action but also commonplace activities and minor movements [12]. The researcher employed tools with a 2D picture creation program in vector format to generate a sharp image format that can be scaled for a number of uses for such character designs.

g) Color selection: Using the graphics program's selected color function, the researcher chose the colors from genuine images gathered from photographs of significant cultural customs.

Figure 2. Characteristics of super-deformed character proportions (Chibi) [11]

2.2. Character elements and strengths expressed for communication

Semiotics has maintained its emphasis on sign interpretation as a means of communication, but the area has fused with various other disciplines, each of which has its own interpretation [13]. Mascot character design emphasizes the use of transmission and transmission attributes to signify happiness, good fortune, and auspiciousness. Consequently, the approach focuses on giving designed mascot characters real meaning. Mascots are amulets, canines, people, or items acquired to bring good fortune to their owners and to showcase their cultural and aesthetic significance. Mascots are classified as static or dynamic. The immobile and non-interactive mascots are immobile and static (e.g., models, statues, images). They can be both analog and digital. Physically and technologically interactive, the dynamic mascots occupy physical space and engage in activities [14]. Techniques can be applied in Phuket towns to bring these art forms to life. In times of rapid cultural change and expanding cultural variety, it is crucial to comprehend the processes of cultural development and change. Culture, identity, and originality are intrinsically interwoven [15]. Incorporating architectural elements into the design: These architectural symbols are intended to demonstrate an effective application of semiotic principles in the perception of national and city identities and to be vocalized by individuals through the process referred to by Sorkin (1999) as "articulation of territory" [16].

2.3. Mascot character for city

Kumamon's fame has had its own impact on the local economy, with item sales reaching around 29.3 billion yen in the first year of his promotion. This sum was extremely close to the total income of the agriculturally renowned Kumamoto Prefecture. The local government also uses the prefecture's mascot in a number of activities and international tourism promotion [17]. Mascots are among the most recognizable forms of advertising. For instance, Ronald McDonald is as familiar as McDonald's famous "Golden Arches" emblem. Ronald McDonald is a symbol of McDonald's that people of all ages recognize worldwide. Using the current influx of social media, utilities now have an excellent platform for projecting a particular image through mascots [5]. The significance of company mascots is heightened by the fact that they express meaning with a single image. If that image is biased, it can function as a lightning rod for public criticism, bringing unwanted attention to the business. Understanding the true cultural weight of mascots as a modern iteration of an early moralistic art form reveals why foreign embassies exploit the cultural weight for diplomatic reasons by adopting this form strategically.

Mascots are deployed in country-to-country relations as opposed to country-to-country ties, circumventing formal institutions to send international signals directly. In this way, mascots are significant as a form of soft power [18]. Utilize the literature to study the data acquired to examine the modelling elements and performance of mascots, the design of mascots in various nations, and national mascots that aim to impart culture and spirit [19]. For the regional mascot's image, it is required to depart from the old image trend of animals and create additional alterations to the mascot's traits. The design should embrace the regional culture, fauna, humanities, and landscape vegetation in their entirety [20]. Putting a familiar face on the biodiversity problem and relying on people's intense loyalty to their teams and mascots could persuade people who would not otherwise pay for conservation to do so. With millions of worldwide supporters for each league, the pool of potential benefactors is vast [21]. The existence of a mascot as a creative representation by emphasizing the visual character that can leave a lasting impact on people's minds, and reinforce the brand's identity.

3. METHOD

- a) Gain an understanding of the arts, culture, and customs of the people of Phuket, targeting the distinctive qualities of the values of other civilizations. It is unique to Phuket because it collects a lot of information about things like the region's art, culture, identity, traditions, symbols, and Phuket's identity. Cultural model tradition and art used in these designs are:
 - Baba Yaya: Tradition of Peranakan dressing in Phuket.
 - O-Tao: A dish similar to fried clams mixed with flour and seasonings, which is a local food that can be found in Phuket area.
 - O-Aew: A dessert or a local dish in Phuket. Looks like clear ice There are many forms of ingredients.
 - Ocean: Factors in lifestyle that are consistent with sea voyages that affect the beliefs, culture, and arts of Phuket people.
 - A traditional festival celebrated in August by Chinese-origin Phuket inhabitants. During a ceremony honouring ancestors, flour-based delicacies in the shape of a big turtle are offered as sacrifices.
- b) Create a mascot that embodies the city of Phuket's art, culture, and customs. Do research and gather data on design elements. It is appropriate for character design utilizing symbols of graphic components such as lines, colors, and shapes, and for communicating the character's identity through imaginative computer graphics techniques. The characters' shapes and lines are based on rounded lines, which show that they are gentle, friendly, and kind.

To describe the physical traits of the character, use super-deformed (Chibi) character. It has a look and personality that are easy to express and get to know because the figures' sizes and shapes are appealing and their actions are like those of children. Which brings such information into the process of creating a piece of art through the following processes:

- Silhouette sketch sketching a rough outline of the character to create a preliminary shape to collect ideas and designs.
- Character component design by inserting and distributing the composition of the character to create the proportions and components within the character design.
- Collecting information on character elements: This part of the process is important because it involves adding details so that the character can express the symbols from the details of the elements, whether through the creation of patterns, shapes, or lines, in order to show the different identities of the arts mentioned above.
- Creating and adding colors and shadows: In this process, the creator uses color, light, shadow and detail by referring to the original image that is created to be beautiful and suitable for the inspirational model that has been created.

Whole process is based on the use of basic creativity by using sketch design with artistic skills, drawing and using the tools from computer graphics programs to get the design of the character to enter the next process.

- c) Propose a mascot character design to a qualified individual and enhance the format depending on their suggestions: Using these ideas from an expert's point of view, the design of the mascot character is changed and improved to match the expert's idea.
- d) When these figures were first depicted, the researchers analyzed and evaluated this designed digital image data. Three experts assessed each design element's level of satisfaction. experts in graphic design, character design, and cultural professionals from the Phuket community.
- e) The findings were examined and summarized by the study participants. Inquiries were done, and the data were examined utilizing the mean, standard deviation x , and standard deviation S.D.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher obtained the data format for the aforementioned examples of graphic design. By employing design techniques in sketching and entering the graphic process from both computer and hand and graphics, lines, shapes, and mascot characteristics that are integral to Phuket's creative cultural notions can be created. To build the characters so that this design could be communicated to the audience, the designers gave the characters the ability to exhibit emotions and gestures and a human-like appearance, so that the audience could gain a better understanding of the character's overall personality. Using data on the arts, culture, and customs of the community of Phuket, the creative characters were ranked based on the level of approval from the character design experts who evaluated them. The character style has inherited the shape of the character from the use of the character in human form, although it predominantly uses symbols and shapes from items such as Phuket's cuisine. Using the savory food "O-Tao" as a male character, while the sweet dish "O-Aew" uses a man instead of a woman dressed in a cultural style of clothing to create both characters. The characteristic red turtle buns, which

also reflect the tradition's good fortune, are complementary to the characters designed to promote good fortune and wealth; their colors are extracted from the original image and used to complement the color of the design's characters.

Both character designs use simple shapes to represent signals in order to effectively communicate emotions. A focus on communication to make the characters approachable to the audience. It is also the integration of the various elements to convey to make the mascot character fully as shown in Figures 3 and 4. A mascot's name: "O-Tao from design process as shown in Figure 4. Character design inspired by food culture, savory and food, architectural elements. Representing a masculine personality trait, the use of color from the yellow-toned buildings that are most common in Old Phuket Town.

Figure 3. Mascot characters obtained by taking data to make designs

Figure 4. Mascot characters action, mascot's name "O-Tao"

Character design inspired by the ancient women's dress culture of Old Phuket Town as shown in Figure 5. Representing the main color of the character from the color of the local dessert, which also conveys the beauty of the young woman. Also brings the sea, which is both a natural resource and is related to the culture and lifestyle of Phuket people as well.

A super-deformed (Chibi) character can build designs and compositions for the characters that are exactly suited to the elements and colors in the design. Based on the responses to design issues, the following was determined: the design is consistent with the art, culture, and traditions of the people of Phuket. Therefore, cultural design is crucial for the digital era in order to better comprehend the context of numerous cultures and to effectively mix commodities with the uses and ways of life of other cultures [22]. Tradition and lifestyle are design pillars.

Figure 5. Mascot characters action, mascot's name "O-Aew"

While studying graphic design, you can hone your creative skills in traditional graphic design. By communicating the characters, people can be made aware of Phuket's symbols. The collection of cultural objects might be classified initially based on their appearance, usage behavior, or philosophy. Ideology is based

on a particular meaning, story, emotions, and other abstract symbols, as well as other projects that may constitute a crucial element of the design theme of cultural goods as a component of the transition [23]. This current research and development project creates new corporate identities that are shown through the traits of mascots (characters) that can be used to make a wide range of other products. All of these products can be designed in a way that shows how they all fit together in a methodical and sophisticated way [24]. Characters that incorporate cultural and artistic elements are valuable. With the development of industry and technology, artistic concepts shifted, and the aesthetic of meaninglessness and simple geometric patterns evolved [25]. Phuket locals' customs are included in the overall design. With the addition of traditional graphic design, you can attempt to design and create works with a sense of time and history while incorporating the students' own aesthetic sensibilities and the diverse emotional components found in traditional culture. By employing design techniques in sketching and entering the graphic process from both computer and hand graphics, lines, shapes, and mascot characteristics that are integral to Phuket's creative and cultural notions can be created. This is the initial step of the digital transformation of Phuket's cultural values as a mascot. This is the technique of utilizing technology to generate and design, modify, and transmit these artistic symbols. In addition, having such an exceptional creative style can give beauty to this design, making it a type of creativity derived from other designs. The researcher has created a 3D character from a 2D character image.

Using technological tools to develop in both directions, the process is viewed as a technique to expand the creative work. Work in graphic design and the transfer of artistic and cultural concepts along the road. It is evident that the designers of these works utilized technology and contributed innovative concepts to the arts. In addition to technological advancement, culture has also been transmitted as a type of progress. The city has also become an important cultural capital with revival potential. By evaluating the themes, color principles, and structural components in relation to artistic expression and the profound cultural significance of oriental aims [26], [27].

Creating inspiration and creativity by using creative technological processes or other methods. It can be further developed from recognizing and transmitting inspiration and transforming the perceived image. In this study, we have used graphic technology tools to help spread and extend the culture to spread and spread more widely. Starting from culture, passing on to creating graphics in different ways, as shown in Figure 6, from the creation of 2D characters to pass on to 3D creations.

The use of computer technology in designing, transferring, and maintaining a graphic work in the form of a mascot character, based on the concept and inspiration of design in art and culture, and transmitting this concept through other associated technologies in order to produce different types of work, whether in the design sector or in other fields. That brings the value of art and culture and well-being through interpretation with the art and tools of technology and computers today. This can be explained by the schematic shown in the Figure 7.

Figure 6. Characters from the 2D creation to design to create a 3D character style

Figure 7. The concept of transmitting artistic and cultural values through design tools in other design forms. or other fields of knowledge

5. CONCLUSION

A case study of the character given by the artistic and cultural value of Phuket Province using various concepts, theories, and design techniques was developed and applied in design, such as the introduction of character creation patterns through the study of physical show design, human impersonation, and combining symbolic shapes with imagination. The outcomes of this study's mascot figure design reflect the singularity of the arts. This study aims to examine Phuket's cultural traditions, as stated in its purpose. Incorporating this character's design into additional works is permissible. This design strategy and method resulted in the creation of mascot characters with exceptional performance. Phuket city's physical make-up, customs, culture, and other cultural values. The creation of mascots is the outcome of the mix of artistic skills and cartoon character design. It is a cartoon symbol that the viewer must remember in order to obtain something intriguing, valuable in terms of beauty and uniqueness, and memorable. It can be demonstrated that these information concepts can be used as creative tools that have been transformed into conceptual assets, and that creativity has not just increased in the manufacture of mascot figures. Such auspicious value and cost can also be exploited for a variety of creative purposes, including graphic design, multimedia design, and adding cultural costs to digital art, indicating that the adoption of a cost basis for cultural art has been effective. It can be combined with a variety of sciences to widen the job's scope and serve as a bridge to encourage creativity and greater imagination. Using the creative technology tools that have been regarded as one of the factors in aiding the preservation of people's art and culture in order to continue to expand and expand in various channels of media creation, or the process of utilizing other forms of technology with a combination of diverse bodies of knowledge; furthermore, the transmission of art through these media conversions contributes to the development of a public relations strategy for the city that employs the concept of utilizing the cultural traditions of the city or province to increase the city's visibility. The establishment of a second channel that allows visitors to view images and stories of cartoon characters as a means of promoting the area's image through local cartoon characters will help to stimulate a great deal of curiosity and memory, as well as expand the audience and interest base. When a graphic prototype is used to generate a schematic as an example in production and design, this is evident. Utilization of other creative technologies can be enhanced.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Jirawat Sookkaew is lecture in major of Computer graphic and multimedia, Faculty of Information and communication technology, University of Phayao. My Bachelor degree in Arts field of Interactive and game design development. His Master degree is Industrail Education design. Specializes in graphic design, multimedia, interactive media, and digital art design. He can be contacted at email: Jirawat.so@up.ac.th.

Asst. Prof. Dr. Nakarin Chaikaew he is a Ph.D. in Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems, Asian Institute of Technology (AIT). Assistant Professor in Geographic Information Science, University of Phayao, Thailand. He can be contacted at email: Nakarin.ch@up.ac.th.

Pipatpong Saephoo Lecturer of Digital Business in the faculty of information and communication technology, University of Phayao. My educations in Bachelor degree is Business Computer and Master degree is Information Systems, Australia. My interested research areas are information system, data analytics, the development of web application and mobile application. He can be contacted at email: Pipatpong.sa@up.ac.th.